

WAYS TO IMPROVE LISTENING SKILLS AMONG CHILDREN

Firdavs Bekzodovich Jumayev

Graduate pupil of general secondary school № 70, Narpay district, Samarkand region

Bekzod Normurodovich Jumayev

Scientific supervisor

Annotation: This article discusses the ways and methods of solving problems related to listening skills in the process of teaching foreign languages to children.

Keywords: interesting methods, exercises, activity, "Spelling", step-by-step exercises, vocabulary.

Introduction: Today, learning foreign languages is becoming the need of the hour. We all know that the English language has become one of the most widely spoken languages in the world, that the need for this language is increasing in our country, and that this language is used in every field.

The fact that English language teaching starts at preschool and school age is one of the opportunities created for Uzbekistan to compete with foreign countries in various fields. Learning foreign languages helps children to develop a world view, to communicate truly, to express their thoughts openly, to better understand cultures and to be capable in many other areas. In this process, the ability to listen is important.

Listening is an important element of learning English as a foreign language. Listening is a form of communication. According to statistics, people spend 70-80% of their day communicating in some way, and about 55% of that is spent listening. Also, listening is the most interesting part of learning English.

The great English writer William Shakespeare said: "Listen more, speak less." In our opinion, with these words, the writer explained that listening is more important than speaking. When we talk, we express only a limited opinion. It does not matter how much we know, but we are little compared to those who need knowledge. In listening, you can evaluate ideas that are different from what we believe, expand our worldview, learn more and new things and teach them. It can change our perception of the world around us.

"Of all the leadership skills, listening is one of the most valuable and least understood. Most industry leaders sometimes listen and become ordinary leaders. But a few greats don't stop listening. That is, they are aware of invisible problems and opportunities before anyone else," Peter Nulty reported in Fortune magazine [1].

Many students, mainly elementary school students, have problems with listening because English is a new language. During this period, their vocabulary is limited or they can only hear that word, but they cannot remember the necessary words. In their book Listening, Anne Anderson and Tony Lynch recommend that "Young listeners with poor memory and listening skills are not helped by extra information in redundant messages, because they will have a lot of information to process. That is why it is necessary to use tasks made up of simple words during the lesson for children of junior school age" [2].

In order to improve students' listening ability, teachers should pay more attention during the lesson and teach through easy and interesting methods. In addition, parents should also help their children improve their listening skills. There are many games that teachers can use to improve listening skills in class. For example, one of the interesting games is "Simon Says" [3]. Children love this game because it keeps them active. Teachers can also increase the listening factor by saying: Simon says, "Tap the thing that starts with the letter 'A'." Students run around the classroom and find something that starts with the letter "A". They can also perform ridding and various animal tricks. It depends only on the imagination of the teachers, but it is very good to use it. This is a great game for elementary school students to use in the classroom.

The dictation method is also useful for improving the listening skills of young students. Depending on the class of the students, the teacher says easier or slightly more complicated words orally. For example, for second-graders, it spells out the word, that is, "Spelling", which improves both writing and listening skills. Also, using three-step exercises during classes is one of the useful methods [5]. These stages include preparation for listening to information, hearing it and analyzing it. The pre-listening phase helps our students prepare for what they want to hear and it helps them succeed in any task, helps teachers determine what students already know about the subject, prepares students for the vocabulary and language structures in the text.

A listening stage is a series of activities that a student performs while listening to a passage to demonstrate their understanding of what has been heard. Well-designed activities help students: identify what is important in a passage, understand text structure, and learn to focus. The main purpose of the post-listening phase is to help students reflect on their listening experience. These exercises are carried out after the teacher has successfully completed the pre-listening and listening activities. This step is for checking and summarizing. One activity the teacher can do to check for understanding is to ask the student to summarize what they have heard, which can be done orally or in writing.

Conclusion: *In conclusion, we can say that listening is one of the most important aspects of foreign language learning for everyone. These steps are useful not only for schoolchildren, but also for university students. To develop it, it is advisable to watch more cartoons and videos with subtitles, listen to songs from a young age. The above steps are useful not only for schoolchildren, but also for university students. A child's reading, writing and speaking skills develop well through listening and understanding. Parents and teachers should work together to develop them.*

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